

Bidirectional assistive logic for longitudinal glide dynamics of a wingsuit

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Abstract—The longitudinal dynamics of a wingsuit is investigated by analyzing the strengths and limitations of an assistive control system. We propose a control logic that reproduces the control modality used by a flying flyer driving the suit when following a desired descent trajectory specified by waypoints. The control logic is based on a discrete-time PID controller with the error on the body angle as input and the force that the flyer delivers as output. From this, a bidirectional thrust is designed to support it during turning maneuvers to follow arbitrary trajectories. Finally, the benefits that this solution can provide to the aviator’s health are also evaluated.

Index Terms—Assistive control, falling, human-machine interaction, human-machine cooperation, wearable robot, wingsuit.

I. INTRODUCTION

A wingsuit is a wearable suit made of an appropriate flexible material, intimately connected to the body and designed to maximize the free fall time or the glide ratio of the wearer [1]. Actually, it is also the only wearable solution to fly that can be used for high-altitude flights. The basic working principle of a wingsuit is to generate lift through the webbing distributed between the arms, legs, and body. An airfoil made of two layers of fabric allows air to flow into the ribs, creating high pressure within the wing [2], [3]. In this study, our interest is evaluating the usability of an automatic control scheme that assists the glide of a flyer wearing a wingsuit. Specifically, the longitudinal dynamics of a wingsuit is investigated by analyzing the strengths and limitations of an assistive control system. We propose a control logic that mimics the control mode used by a human wearing a wingsuit when following a desired descent trajectory specified by a sequence of waypoints. Building on these results, our goal is to define a control logic for a thruster located at the flyer’s feet that can support the aviator while executing maneuvers without requiring a change in the wingsuit’s steering strategy.

II. POWERED WINGSUIT SYSTEM MODELING

Our purpose is to evaluate the dynamic effects produced by the rotation of the flyer’s body during a longitudinal maneuver jointly with the effect of a thruster not applied in the aviator’s center of gravity. The flyer’s effect enters the system dynamics as a force F (either positive or negative), acting at the shoulder level, which generates a momentum that causes the rotation of

the flyer’s body in the counterclockwise or clockwise direction. In contrast, a thrust generator (secured to the flyer’s feet) delivers a positive force T at an angle $\chi = \pm 90^\circ$ with respect to the axis of the body. Overall, the system dynamics is summarized in the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} &= V \cos(\theta) \\ \dot{y} &= V \sin(\theta) \\ m \dot{V} &= m g \sin(\theta) - D + T \cos(\theta - \beta + \chi) - F \sin(\theta - \beta) \\ m V \dot{\theta} &= m g \cos(\theta) - L - T \sin(\theta - \beta + \chi) - F \cos(\theta - \beta) \\ I \dot{\beta} &= l T \sin(\chi) - b F \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where x is the frontal displacement, y is the downward displacement, V is the magnitude of the velocity, θ is the glide angle, β is the body pitch angle, m is the mass of the flyer wearing wingsuit, g is the gravitational acceleration, D is the drag, L is the total lift, I is the moment of inertia of the body, l is the moment arm of the thruster and b is the moment arm of the flyer’s force.

III. FREE-FALLING DYNAMICS

Before evaluating the presence of the flyer and thruster forces, it is crucial to study the dynamics of the wingsuit in free-falling, i.e., in the absence of external control forces ($F = T = 0$). The system equilibrium points are derived by imposing the state derivative in (1) equal to zero. However, without external forces, the wingsuit is a free-falling system that naturally tends to fall toward the ground. Consequently, it is logical to expect that \dot{x} and \dot{y} cannot equal 0. For this reason, we simply compute the system equilibrium state with the exception of states (x, y) . The simplified system of equations is given by (2).

$$\begin{cases} D = m g \sin(\theta) \\ L = m g \cos(\theta) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Computing the ratio between the two equations in (2), a new equation that relates the state variable θ with the ratio between the drag force D and the total lift L is achieved, that is written in (3)

$$\tan(\theta) = \frac{D}{L} \quad (3)$$

The equilibrium values of θ and $\frac{D}{L}$ that satisfy (3) can be computed by numerical simulation.

IV. CONTROLLED FALLING DYNAMICS

Unlike the dynamics in free-falling, in which the trajectory followed by the wingsuit is decided by the initial state variables and, therefore, the system is in free evolution; in the dynamics of controlled falling, the contribution of both the flyer and the thruster is important and determines the descent trajectory. In Section IV-A, we initially propose a human-like controller that emulates the driving logic of a person who wants to follow a trajectory made of waypoints. Then, the relative thrust control to reduce the effort made by the pilot is illustrated in Section IV-B. For simplicity, we consider that the flyer knows the coordinates of the target points it needs to reach and can estimate the ϕ angle at which the targets are located with respect to its position.

A. Human-like feedback control scheme

To reproduce the driving response produced by a human flyer, we considered a discrete-time PID controller with the error on the angle β as input and the force F that the flyer delivers as output. During each maneuver, two phases can occur: one defined Approaching Phase, in which the person tries to reach a target point, and the other defined Stabilization Phase, in which the person implements a more conservative control policy, returning the body to a safer position (angle). The human-like control we propose in this study provides satisfactory control for both operating phases. The control logic and controller parameters are the same in both cases; they differ only in the input reference signal to the controller.

1) *Body angle control*: Let us consider the LTI state-space representation derived from (1) and reported in (4-5) in which the state variables are β and $\dot{\beta}$, the input signal is F , and the output signal is β .

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\beta} \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_A \begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ \dot{\beta} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -b/I \end{bmatrix}}_B F \quad (4)$$

$$[\beta] = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_C \begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ \dot{\beta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Based on the above LTI representation, we tuned a discrete PD-type controller that provides the value of the flyer's force F starting from an angle error E_β and having the following form:

$$\frac{F(z)}{E_\beta(z)} = K_p + K_d \frac{f_s}{\frac{f_s}{N} + \frac{1}{z-1}} \quad (6)$$

2) *Approaching control*: The force F delivered by the flyer, in the absence of the thrust T , is the only force acting on the wingsuit that generates an angular momentum M , thus changing the body angle β and, consequently, the glide angle θ and the speed V . By appropriately calibrating this force, the glide angle θ can be changed to converge toward the target. Based on this principle, we assume that the wingsuit flyer is sufficiently experienced to know the angle of the body at which it has to position itself to change the glide angle and reach the target. In summary, during the approaching control

phase, the flyer first determines the target angle ϕ , then the angle β_T at which it has to position itself, and finally delivers a force F , according to the control law (6), in which the input is the angle error $E_\beta = \beta_T - \beta$.

3) *Stabilizing control*: Since the flyer delivers a force F to track the target angle ϕ , this force could generate an undesired angular momentum that could cause the system to rotate excessively. The stabilization control is designed within the human-like control system to limit this rotation and is based on a threshold logic. If the angle of the flyer's body exceeds a given threshold, it neglects the pursuit of the target angle ϕ and delivers the force F to stabilize itself.

B. Thruster control scheme

Thruster control is designed to support the flyer maneuvers. This translates into a continuous thrust force that follows the force F generated by the flyer during the flight. In other words, the flyer does not have to change its steering logic due to the introduction of the thruster. The flyer only limits the force generated because the thruster is able to deliver the remaining necessary force within certain limits. This type of assisted support is known in the literature as Human-Machine Interaction (HMI) or Human-Machine Cooperation (HMC) [4].

1) *Assistive control*: The contribution delivered by the thrust T along the angular direction χ must produce the same effect that the force F alone, applied perpendicularly to the flyer axis, would have. If this were not the case, the flyer would perceive an unexpected force that would change the natural guidance of the wingsuit. Given that the thrust is bidirectional, the angle χ defines the direction of the thrust. If $\chi = 90^\circ$, the thrust is directed upward; otherwise, if $\chi = -90^\circ$, the thrust is directed downward. Thus, the thruster positions itself, upward or downward, depending on the force F direction (i.e., $\chi = 90^\circ$ if $F < 0$ and $\chi = -90^\circ$ if $F > 0$). Once the angle χ has been derived, we need to calculate the thruster force T that instantaneously has to be delivered to reduce the physical effort made by the flyer by a factor γ . This value is given in equation (7), where $|F|$ represents the absolute value of the force F .

$$T = (\gamma - 1) \frac{b}{I} |F| \quad (7)$$

2) *Stabilization control*: The stabilization control applied by the thruster is analogous to its counterpart used by the human-like controller.

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